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Public-Police-Partnership to improve safety and security measures in Higher Education Institutions: A systematic study South Africa.

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Abstract

Safety and security are the most basic needs for humans and societies. This is the most fundamental need, and their absence renders individuals vulnerable. The safety/security measures are ranked second (after physiological needs) by Abraham Maslow's classic work on human needs ranked. This paper uses a systematic study to establish the essentiality of public-police partnership (PPP) in improving safety and security measures in higher education institutions (HEIs). Selected common crimes (sexual harassment, Gender-based violence, and theft) are going to form the crux of this paper. This qualitative paper followed a systematic review, as a research design restricted from 2015 to 2024. The new Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) reporting guidelines of 2020 supported this research design and approach. The Qualitative Content Analysis (QCA) was adopted to locate existing scholarly accredited journals, books, print and online newspaper reports, internet sources, social science databases, and governmental documents/gazettes for data collection. The findings of this paper emphasise the ignored collaboration of different stakeholders in the HEIs exist. Moreover, the safety and security, investigative team, Community Policing Forums (CPFs) and private security companies, and South African Police Service (SAPS) are working in silos to achieve efficient campus safety. Their significance in fighting various crimes within university premises is undermined. It has also been established that basic security measures training for the university population is unfounded, resulting in many students falling victim to crime. This paper recommends that the HEIs students, when walking at night, must avoid walking alone and should walk in groups; when walking, they must avoid having headphones, as they lessen their ability to be vigilant and become suitable targets owing to their valuable asserts. The relevant stakeholders should normalise working together through the application of the PPP. This paper addresses the gap in the existing literature to enforce collaborations of relevant stakeholders using the PPP in the HEIs.

Keywords: *Crime, Higher Education Institutions, Public-Police-Partnership, Safety and security measures, Systematic study, Universities.*

Introduction

In a population, security is an essential need for individual and societal growth. This argument is reinforced by Kiran and Taj (2022), who argue that Higher Education Institutions (HEI) safety is a collective challenge for all key stakeholders. The term security is used in various contexts; therefore, security can be defined as a safeguard against vulnerability, violence, distress, and want that harms citizens' total progress and existential well-being (Leaning & Arie, 2000; Brauch, 2008; Okolie, 2022). According to Abiodun (2016), security is the most fundamental necessity of persons and communities. Similarly, security is regarded as a basic human need, with its absence

rendering individuals unproductive in many parts of life. Universities are higher education institutions where students gain crucial skills for personal and societal development; students must feel comfortable and secure. In Abraham Maslow's landmark study on human needs, safety/security placed second (after physiological) in the hierarchy of human wants (Abiodun, Ademola, Chinedu, & Victoria, 2020). The absence of fear and desire suggests safety, the latter scholars agree.

Ross and Rasool (2019) argue that contacts with criminality have major psychological, financial, and academic consequences for students, which is consistent with cognitive behavioural theory. Students employed a number of cognitive and behavioural techniques to deal with the ordeal of crime (Ross & Rasool, 2019; Sumi, Woodbridge, Wei, Thornton, & Roundfield, 2021). Students suggested that universities increase security measures such as patrols and CCTV surveillance cameras, and that students adopt self-protection measures such as walking in groups, being more vigilant, and not wearing headphones while walking (Ross & Rasool, 2019; Moulton, 2019; Mwiti, 2023; Ceccato, Langefors, & Näsman, 2023). These ideas for increasing guardianship by university security and police, together with student self-protection methods, have the ability to lower the likelihood of students being targets of criminal offenders (Ross & Rasool, 2019). Unfortunately, institutions of higher learning face security hazards that expose students to security threats such as sexual harassment, burglary, robbery, and bullying.

Institutions of higher study can be accessible targets for criminals. According to Ross and Rasool (2019), students arrive on campus and leave with fear. Ceccato, Langefors, and Näsman (2023) agree with the latter authors, noting that learners' mobility is influenced by their fear of crime. As a result, as a precaution, individuals will avoid locations where they are afraid of crime. However, when they need to visit specific locations, they will most likely avoid them at specific times. Langefors and Näsman (2023) suggest that when people are less afraid of crime, they are more likely to stay in those areas beyond the needed activities. The HEI environment is more than simply a location for teaching and learning; it's also a hub for networking, sports, and other leisure activities. Makhaye, Mkhize and Sibanyoni (2023) support this assertion, arguing that Campus is a generally open and accessible place that promotes intellectual, social, and physical activities for students' overall growth. Learners would like to remain within the university premises beyond the study hours; nevertheless, with the fear of crime, they would be forced to be on the university grounds only when necessary.

Ross and Rasool (2019), in their study, indicated that student participants are afraid to travel alone during sunset hours; they fear being attacked or victimised. Those who have been victims of crime already within the university precinct confided. The student participant expressed their fear that a vehicle could stop in front of them and someone from the car would get out of the vehicle and demand the student items while showing a weapon to instil fear (Ross & Rasool, 2019). The safety and risks those HEI in South Africa are exposed to undermine the country's hard-fought democracy while undermining the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal number 16, that is meant to address all forms of violence.

South Africa suffers an exceptional international problem of violence, which is harmful to our society since it undermines our nation's democratic foundations, social progress, and health, Bezuidenhout (2020) contends. The third quarter (October - December 2022) crime figures provided by the then South African Police Minister Bheki Cele on February 17, 2023, reflect a rise in contact crimes such as murder, assault, and robberies occurred in South Africa. This is a drawback in attaining goals three and 16 of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (2030). Therefore, this paper seeks to contribute to the promotion of the UN'SDGs, particularly goal 16, whilst also the paper contributes to evaluating one of the objectives of the South African National Development Plan (2030), objective 12 or NDP chapter 12: Building safer communities. Thus, the paper seeks to contribute to this chapter (12). The findings of this paper add to the importance of building safer communities, specifically for the higher institution population. Whilst epitomising chapter 12 of NDP, as stated by NDP 2030;

“An integrated approach to safety and security will require coordinated activity across various departments, the private sector and community bodies, the latter to include revitalised community-safety centres”.

This paper aims to analyse the policing partnership between South African Police Service (SAPS), Private Security Companies, HEI and the Community Policing Forums in ensuring safety in the HEI in SA. This objective precisely embodies Chapter 12 of the NDP 2030. The paper further aims to determine the prevalence of violence and its impact on social development, democracy, and students' health in higher learning institutions in SA. The paper aims to determine the cooperation of the HEI in South Africa with the SAPS, Private security companies and Community policing forum in policing the following crimes: Sexual harassment, Gender-based violence (GBV) and Robbery.

Method

The paper used the newly Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). Gathering sufficient data for analysis and surfing the internet by the authors took about a year. Search engines such as ResearchGate, Google Scholar and various Department of Higher Education (DHET) accredited journal websites were browsed through. The inclusion criterion for the data collection required papers with dominant concepts such as safety, security, institutions of higher learning, sexual harassment, GBV, robbery, SAPS, and community policing forums. The mentioned concepts were vital for the authors in their data collection quest. Content qualitative analysis was used to produce the formidably concrete paper. While the data collection by the authors was in progress, the data analysis was done concurrently. The data was examined as the authors gathered it; this allowed the authors to familiarise themselves with the content of the information found, whilst new concepts were identified and explored as the analysis progressed. The literature review in the following section commences with sexual harassment deliberation.

Literature review

Sexual harassment

As mentioned, “in the preamble of the Criminal Law (Sexual Offences and Related Matters) Amendment Act 32 of 2007, the prevalence of the commission of sexual offences in our society is primarily a social phenomenon, which is reflective of deep-seated, systematic dysfunctionality in our society”. Rape is defined as an illegal and purposeful act of sexual intercourse with another person without their permission (Klopper & Bezuidenhout, 2020). Rape is a subcategory of sexual violence. Whilst sexual harassment is defined by Rostami, Ghazinour, Burman and Hansson (2022: p.3) as “any form of unwanted verbal, non-verbal or physical conduct of a sexual nature occurs, with the purpose or effect of violating the dignity of a person, in particular when creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment”. Sexual harassment can manifest as verbal for example, sexual remarks, demands for favours or nonverbal for example, exhibitionism, sexual gestures, gazing or physical example bodily contact, sexual assault (Salisu, Aliyu, & Anwar, 2021; Hardt, Stöckl, Wamoyi, & Ranganathan, 2023).

Sexual harassment is seen as a widespread problem that affects a diverse community. However, Akram and Yasmin (2023) claim that there is still a lack of studies on sexual violence against women, making it one of the most ignored topics of research in Pakistan. While in South Africa (SA) the data on rape illustrate far more significant than similar nations, Bezuidenhout (2020) asserted. The minister of police, Bheki Cele, raised concern that a total of 5 935 rape occurrences occurred at the perpetrator or victim's house, including residences known by the victims/perpetrator, implying that they are relatives, friends, and neighbours. Females are commonly considered the victims, whilst males are the offenders of sexual offences (Javaid, 2015).

Institutions of higher learning are not immune from the incidences of rape. Hardt et al., (2023) emphasise that offenders of sexual harassment might include supervisors, instructors, colleagues, service providers, and opposite gender counterpart in the community and at educational settings. Adding that sexual harassment in higher education settings has a detrimental influence on female students' involvement and performance, as well as the general learning atmosphere. Sexual harassment could be inflicted through demanding sexual favours from learners while refusing awarding well deserved grading if learners refuses, (Salisu, Aliyu, & Anwar, 2021).

Sexual offences committed on HEI have been identified as a public health risk (Fedina, Holmes, & Backes 2018, p.77). According to Phipps, Ringrose, Renold, and Jackson (2018), sexual assaults on universities continue to be prevalent. Similarly, Riwanto, Harisudin, and Firmandiaz (2023) agree that sexual harassment on campus is a prevalent issue that affects institutions of learning internationally. Safety in South African Institutions of Higher learning remains a challenge. Hashtags such as #Endrapeculture broke out and spread throughout SA university campuses in April 2016 (Orth, Van Wyk, & Andipatin, 2020). These protests aimed to bring about awareness of university regulations governing rape and sexual assault cases on campus. The demonstrators accused the university administration of supporting a rape culture through existing rules that supported victim-blaming while shielding criminals of sexual assaults.

With hashtag movements and public marches, the cause quickly garnered traction on social and mainstream media. This movement increased pressure on university administrators to hold sexual assault incidences on campus responsible. Each public institution has a policy in place to address sexual assault, harassment, or rape on campus involving a student or university staff. These rules describe sexual harassment and sexual assault, as well as the institutions' position on such actions and the processes for dealing to accusations of sexual harassment and sexual assault (Orth, Van Wyk, & Andipatin, 2020).

Initiatives criticising higher education for supporting a culture of rape are not restricted to South Africa; comparable initiatives have been established on university campuses all around the world. These movement

depicts that sexual harassment within the university setting is not only a South African problem; for example, Universities have been accused of promoting “sex for grades, phenomena where some male lecturers have harassed female students when the students fail to submit to the lecturer’s sexual demands” (Kiran & Taj, 2022, p.8311). Nevertheless, sexual harassment in higher institutions occurs in different forms.

Reference from a systematic study conducted by Fedina, Holmes, and Backes (2018) submits that college learners’ experience of sexual offences takes place in different forms. Therefore, intervention from the institution must be related to the form of sexual victimisation a student experience. Regarding the high prevalence of unwanted sexual contact and coercion, they suggested that the intervention efforts must focus on the dynamics of such victimisation. Noting the disproportionate rate of victimisation among learners from minority populations such as LGBTQ, a student with a disability, and racial and ethnic minorities indicates the need for inclusive and culturally specific responses to victims (Fedina, Holmes, & Backes, 2018). The study of Riwanto, Harisudin, and Firmandiaz (2023) demonstrates that the implementation of legislative rules and collaboration governance may dramatically reduce campus sexual assault in Indonesia. Finding effective measures to address the sexual violence within HEI of learning is critical similarly identifying the aspects that makes the HEI vulnerable to the compromise of its population safety is key.

Oni and Tshitangano (2019) identified aspects that made HEI in SA susceptible to the risk of sexual offences. These risk factors affect not only students but also employees of the university. These risk factors included a lack of policy implementation on sexual harassment (Kiran & Taj, 2022), the structure of the university social community alcohol and substance abuse, and lastly, the failure of victims of sexual harassment to report the victimisation (Oni & Tshitangano, 2019). The latter scholars further claim that the offenders of the sexual harassment could be a colleague, senior staff member, personnel at management level or a learner whilst asserting that the victim and the offender could be at the same age.

While on the other hand, Oni and Tshitangano (2019) reported that SA studies depicted that 30% of high school female students had been raped and sexually harassed by fellow male learners and by teachers. Whilst in the institutions of higher learning, the studies on the extent of rape and sexual harassment are scant; thus, the extent of rape and sexual harassment in South African universities remains unknown (Oni & Tshitangano, 2019; Makhaye et al., 2023). Nevertheless, a study by Machisa, Chirwa, Mahlangu, Sikweyiya, Nunze, Dartnall and Jewkes (2021) revealed the ongoing incidences of students who are females experiencing sexual victimisation in the SA higher education context. Meanwhile, Oni and Tshitangano (2019) reveal that a survey done in Malawi found 67% of sexual harassment on campus and 12.6% of students being raped.

While research on sexual harassment in the United States higher education institutions claims that the offence occurs more frequently than individuals realise. Research from Brown University in the United States discovered that 6% of 234 female students attempted rape, and 3.8% reported rape (Deredzaik, Goronga & Maupa, 2024). While Tang, Critelli and Porter (1995) uncovered that the Chinese University of Hong Kong in China among undergraduate female students found that 14.9% of the participants reported attempted rape and 1.4% reported rape. Kiran and Taj (2022) suggest that fewer studies are available in Pakistan, which brings to awareness the occurrences and consequences of sexual harassment for the education of female students at the university level. Sexual harassment victims are reported to demonstrate cognitive, behavioural, emotional, and physical symptoms; these adversities may prolong for some time, even after the sexual harassment has stopped (Oni & Tshitangano, 2019). This means that the sexual offences experienced by the university community may have an everlasting impact, which can change the lifestyle of the victim. The HEI are not only susceptible to sexual violence crime, but robbery is also another common crime that jeopardises safety of campus population.

Robbery

Robbery is defined by Klopper and Bezuidenhout (2020) as theft of property by illegally and purposefully employing violence to obtain property from someone using threats of violence to force the proprietor of the property to acquiesce to the taking thereof. Robbery is categorised as one of the violent crimes that is deemed unacceptable in modern societies. When one contemplates being a victim of such violent crime, it shivers one's spine (Klopper & Bezuidenhout, 2020).

In their study, *Towards Peaceful University Campuses in Nigeria*, Abiodun, Ademola, Chinedu, and Victoria (2020) provided a summarily outline of the safety situation in selected Nigerian campuses. They assert that security maintenance within the campus is a significant challenge exacerbated by the university management's lack of attention. Similarly, in South African institutions of higher learning, Ross and Rasool (2019) suggest that consistently with the Routine Activity Theory (RAT), learners are vulnerable targets due to an absence of protection and, thus, targeted by inspired criminals. Abiodun et al., (2020) argue that the security threat within university campuses is instigated either by internal or external sources. On May 26, 2017, students at Cross Rivers

State University of Technology, Calabar, protested because of security challenges that have consistently threatened them on campus. Similarly, in South African universities, students reported experiencing robbery in the form of theft of their laptops and cellphones and robberies at their residential accommodations (Ross & Rasool, 2019). While robbery is more common to the HEI, GBV is another form of crime that SA institutions must deal with.

Gender-based violence

Former Police Minister Bheki Cele has declared that police are improving their operational and legal responses to GBV and femicide. The minister noted that the “Criminal Law (Forensic Procedures) Amendment Act”, popularly known as the (DNA Act), will enter into action on March 3, 2023. This Act is said to be a significant weapon in the police’s arsenal of crime-fighting tools against GBV to the identification of the offenders. The Act come with great regard by the former police minister in removing serial rapists and ensuring brutality against children, females, and susceptible groups is brought into the book. The former minister announced that between October and December 2022, about 4,992 suspects were arrested for crimes related to GBV. During that reporting period, 71 suspects received 89 life sentences, while 219 were sentenced to one to nine years in incarceration, totalling 1079 years in prison. 143 defendants were sentenced to 10 to 19 years in custody, for a total of 2 063 years. At the same time, 67 additional defendants were sentenced to 20 years or more for GBV-related offences. The minister repeated the appeal for communities to work together with police to prevent and battle GBV and femicide (SAPS, 2023).

Gender-based violence encompasses amongst sexism or biased insight based on gender or sexual identification, sexual aggravation and rape, abuse of power and conflict of interest based on sexual or intimate relations (Underwood, 2019). Kabaya (2021) reported that most participants in her PhD study acknowledged the prevalence of GBV at the institution. One of her participants shared her experience of GBV on campus as follows;

“I have experienced it because I was attacked by three drunk guys trying to go upstairs within the residence. They attacked me. I did not know the people who attacked me, and they were drunk. Two of the SRC members were in the TV room, and when they came out, they told me that they were postgrad students who were here for the graduation and got drunk at the weekend. They attacked me because I wanted to go up the stairs, and they did not want me to go up the stairs. They said I was full of myself, and why did I want to pass while they were still talking to me? When I opened a case, they did nothing until they left. They never questioned them, did not do anything, and never tried to find them. So even the school does nothing” (Kabaya, 202 p.13).

The shared experience of GBV on campus in the above verbatim illustrates that the university management does not take seriously the incidences of GBV student's experiences on campus. The failure of the university to effectively address the issue of GBV on campus further demonstrates that the university does not have sufficient measures/policies designed to address the incidences of GBV happening on campus perpetrated by the university's former students. The GBV in university campuses is not only committed by former students but student leadership is also accused of requesting sexual favours from students in exchange for helping them with finding accommodation. The verbatim below is extracted from a (Kabaya, 202, p.14) study.

“A lot has happened to me. Because the SRC men are involved somehow in assisting with accommodation, so they use their power to ask for sex from us first years because they know that we are in an environment that is not familiar to us and we do not know how things work here. When I came here, it was not easy to get accommodation, and one guy even promised to give me accommodation only if I slept with him. I refused to give in to his demands, and he said he would not help me. I thank God that I managed to get accommodation in the end without having to sleep with anyone, but I know some girls who had to sleep with SRC guys to get accommodation” (Kabaya, 2021).

The perpetuation of GBV on university campuses by student leadership demonstrates a dire situation, as the student leadership should be the guide and ensure the safety of all students. Student leadership should work with university management and security personnel to address and ensure all learners' safety within the university campuses. In the Ngubelanga (2021) master study, 30 per cent of participants said they were safe within the university precinct, while 70 per cent indicated they were unsafe. When those who claimed to be safe were asked why they problematised sexual harassment? They responded that the security personnel cannot protect them in the lecturers and SRC offices and that there are no cameras (Ngubelanga, 2021). The findings from the latter author indicate the in-depth of GBV in institutions of higher learning. Further, it stresses that the GBV in the university campuses is not only perpetrated by outsiders, as lecturers also commit it.

Findings

The study found that different stakeholders within and around the institutions of higher learning need to strive to ensure the university population's safety. This finding is in line with Kiran and Taj (2022), outlining that Parents,

educators, religious groups, nongovernmental organisations, policymakers, and governments all have a shared common desire, which is to ensure the safety of educators, students, as well the other university community members from any imminent danger, which could be a threat in the attainment of educational institution objectives. Nevertheless, the study found that the institutions of higher learning are a battleground for violence globally (Kiran & Taj, 2022).

A study on an inquiry of female campus student's experiences of sexual harassment by Kiran and Taj (2022) found that the majority (90%) of female students at the university claimed having been verbally harassed within and outside the premises of the university daily, whilst other learners reported on being victims of another kind of harassment. The other significant finding of the latter scholars was that harassment negatively affected the education of the victims, as the performance of the victims dropped during the harassment period. An integrated approach, including collaboration between different stakeholders, could play a significant role in protecting students from harassment around institutions of higher learning communities.

A study by Makhaye, Mkhize, and Sibanyoni (2023) identify female students as victims of sexual assault in higher education institutions found that there is insufficient security visibility on the campuses of their study site; their study participants reported that private security companies hardly do patrols on the campuses. Their study participants suggested that security personnel should be visible, particularly when there are events hosted by the campus and on weekends when they reported that acts of sexual crime are on the surge.

Makhaye et al., (2023) study participants took criticism of the security approaches used by the institutions of their study site. The participants argued that the university has resources, such as contracted private security companies, the psychology department, and policies enacted to address sexual harassment; however, the institutions fail to implement their security plans effectively. The questions raised on the approaches the institution of higher learning uses should pave the way for an integrated approach involving close collaboration between the university community, private security companies, SAPS, and community policing forums.

The collaborative approach in the fight against crime in the HEI is supported by Riwanto, Harisudin, and Firmandiaz (2023) study suggesting that the collaborative governance can be achieved through an active engagement by the academic community as well the wider public. Adding that replicating on the success of countries such as United States, Netherland, Canada and United Kingdom developing countries such as Indonesia can reduce sexual crimes on campus. The measures latter scholars referring to which South African institutions may as well adopt include creating legislative laws, forming alliances with central and local governments, and encouraging collaborative governance.

Key measures that have been beneficial in these nations include the formulation of service guidelines that prioritise victim and survivor protection, an enhanced anti-sexual violence campaign on campuses, and the promotion of sexual violence awareness education (Riwanto, Harisudin, & Firmandiaz, 2023).

Ross and Rasool's (2019) study on university students' experiences with crime discovered that learners were disheartened with the police, the university, and university security, who they claimed had ignored to safeguard or assist them in dealing with criminal occurrences. The learners reported that the security personnel are never helpful; they only give excuses when students request to take them to their residence; security officers would say it is against the university policy (Ross & Rasool, 2019). Therefore, security officers accompany students to their places of residence, which requires a change in the university security policy to pave the way or allow security personnel to transport learners to their residences when there is a need or security risk to the learners. Regarding police officers, Ross and Rasool's (2019) study found that they would ask what happened, but no assistance would be attained from them. Students expressed dissatisfaction with the university security measures, as they said they left safety at their homes with the hope that the university would guarantee their safety.

South African institutions and police should work together to improve security by increasing visible surveillance of campus areas, particularly at night. When students have evening classes, need to attend off-site internship training, or comeback from the library in the evening, campus officials must arrange transportation, Ross and Rasool's (2019) study suggested, whilst commending the university of their study site for achieving most of the suggested security measures. They also recommended that students be made aware of crime in and around campus areas and informed of crime hotspots identified by police data. This suggestion further concurs with the authors of this paper, who state that there should be an effective collaboration amongst the higher institutions' community with police officers. Therefore, the police should frequently communicate with the university. The university may also allocate a notice board to communicate information, such as notifications on the new crime trends around the university community.

Ross and Rasool's (2019) study further suggested that learners should not show their possessions or carry excess cash and should keep identity documents and licences in a safe location. Please encourage students to move in groups; however, Makhaye et al. (2023) argued that when students disperse to their rooms, they become

vulnerable to victimisation. Nevertheless, Ross and Rasool (2019) further urged learners to remember emergency contact information and report any unlawful acts to the university and the SAPS. Efforts are also needed to increase public trust in the police and the criminal justice system.

Machisa, Chirwa, Mahlangu, Sikweyiya, Nunze, Dartnall and Jewkes (2021) cross-sectional study found that sexual harassment of female students continues in South African higher education. Furthermore, the study found numerous interconnected features linked to higher susceptibility. TVET college students were more vulnerable, reporting a greater prevalence of sexual violence in the previous year than university students. The research demonstrates the interconnectedness of vulnerability variables affecting female students' experiences with sexual violence.

Orth, Van Wyk and Andipatin (2020, p.1) study on the "perceptions of rape culture on campus and the role of university authorities" claims that supporters of the #Endrapeculture protests believe the university should be held accountable for perpetuating rape culture, while critics believe law enforcement should handle sexual assault cases. This raises issues about the university's role in dealing with sexual assault accusations. Is it sufficient for university administrators to critically re-evaluate their existing sexual assault policies and the tools available to students who report such incidents? The #Endrapeculture demonstrations attempted to spotlight the institution's rape culture and raise awareness about rape in South African society. Orth, Van Wyk and Andipatin (2020) raise integral questions that support the author's view that there is a need for practical cooperation between SAPS and the institutions of higher learning. Universities may not have complete jurisdiction over criminal offences; thus, police officers must be brought in to perform their constitutional obligations to investigate criminal offences and protect citizens.

Discussion - Conclusions

Recommendations

Universities must improve and increase security measures such as patrols and CCTV cameras. The latter should be placed in every corner where learners are most likely to leave their items unattended for a short while; for example, when they go to restrooms, learners cannot be expected to pack and go with their study materials. Students must adopt self-protection measures such as walking in groups or with peers, being more vigilant, and desisting from having headphones on while walking.

The collaboration amongst different stakeholders cannot be more emphasised. The HEI, private security companies, SAPS, community members as well other different stakeholders around the HEI need to come together in ensuring the safety of the campus population.

Strict implementation of sexual harassment policy the HEI to protect its population from within its members. Most institutions are applauded for devising the best policies to protect its members against violation, nevertheless these policies remain impractical if they are not implemented.

Conclusion

The proposed paradigm asserts that safety and security are individuals' and communities' most critical basic needs. As a result, all stakeholders in higher education care should regard safety and security as key. According to the study, a lack of safety and security has significant implications for learners, such as psychological, financial, and physical consequences that may considerably impact teaching and learning. The paper proposes collaboration among HEI, SAPS, CPF, and student self-protection initiatives. Collaboration among these stakeholders might dramatically lower the likelihood of students being easy targets for criminals. Students in higher education institutions are shown to be easy targets for crimes such as sexual harassment, burglary, robbery, and bullying. Students' movements around the institution's perimeter are influenced by their dread of criminal activity. Furthermore, students' fear of crime influences the amount of time they spend at the HEI precinct and their academic work and extracurricular activities. Thus, fear of crime inhibits the student's engagement in other activities accessible to learners at the HEI.

References

- Abiodun, T. F., Ademola, O. E., Chinedu, O. C., & Victoria, O. O. (2020). Towards the Peaceful University Campuses in Nigeria: Urgent call for Strategically-trained and Professional Security Officers. *focus*, 3(1), 44-55.
- Akram, N., & Yasmin, M. (2023, March). Sexual violence against women: Global interventions and an evidence from Pakistan. In *Women's Studies International Forum* (Vol. 97, p. 102691). Pergamon.
- Brauch, H. G. (2008). Conceptualising the environmental dimension of human security in the UN. *International Social Science Journal*, 59, 19-48.
- Ceccato, V., Langefors, L., & Näsman, P. (2023). The impact of fear on young people's mobility. *European Journal of Criminology*, 20(2), 486-506.

- Fedina, L., Holmes, J. L., & Backes, B. L. (2018). Campus sexual assault: A systematic review of prevalence research from 2000 to 2015. *Trauma, violence, & abuse, 19*(1), 76–93.
- Kabaya, S. (2021). *First-year female university residence students' experiences and constructions of gender and sexuality in the context of gender-based violence in South Africa* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Kiran, Z., & Taj, S. (2022). An Investigation Of Female University Students' Experiences Of Sexual Harassment And Its Effects On Their Education. *Webology (ISSN: 1735-188X), 19*(1).
- Klopper, H., and Bezuidenhout, C. (2020). Crimes of a Violent Nature. In C. Bezuidenhout (second edition). *A Southern African Perspective on Fundamental Criminology*. Cape Town. Pearson South Africa.
- Leaning, J., & Arie, S. (2000). *Human security: A framework for assessment in conflict and transition*. Office of Sustainable Development, Bureau for Africa, US Agency for International Development.
- Machisa, M. T., Chirwa, E. D., Mahlangu, P., Sikweyiya, Y., Nunze, N., Dartnall, E., ... & Jewkes, R. (2021). Factors associated with female students' past year experience of sexual violence in South African public higher education settings: A cross-sectional study. *PLoS one, 16*(12), e0260886.
- Maier, S. L., & DePrince, B. T. (2020). College students' fear of crime and perception of safety: The influence of personal and university prevention measures. *Journal of criminal justice education, 31*(1), 63-81.
- Deredzai, M., Goronga, P., & Maupa, B. (2024). Perceptions of Female Students on Strategies to Curb Sexual Harassment: The Case of one Selected Teacher's College in Zimbabwe. *Journal of African Education and Traditional Learning Systems, 5*(2), 79-96.
- Hardt, S., Stöckl, H., Wamoyi, J., & Ranganathan, M. (2023). Sexual harassment in low-and middle-income countries: a qualitative systematic review. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse, 24*(5), 3346-3362.
- Makhaye, M. S., Mkhize, S. M., & Sibanyoni, E. K. (2023). Female students as victims of sexual abuse at institutions of higher learning: insights from Kwazulu-natal, South Africa. *SN social sciences, 3*(2), 40.
- Moult, K. (2019). The state of the nation's crime. *South African Crime Quarterly, (68)*, 3-5.
- Mwiti, A. M. (2023). security awareness and students'safety in selected universities in kenya.
- Ngubelanga, N. L. (2021). *Understanding the factors contributing to sexual harassment amongst black African university students* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Ogbeme, T. A. (2017). 'Students Unrest on Campuses and the Society'. Vanguard newspaper, 13 June, 2017.
- Okolie, U. C. (2022). The distinction between Traditional security and modern security: A conceptual discourse. *Journal of Administrative Science, 19*(2), 247-266.
- Oni, H., & Tshitangano, T. (2019). Sexual harassment and victimization of students: a case study of a higher education institution in South Africa. *African health sciences, 19*(1), 1478-1485.
- Orth, Z., Van Wyk, B., & Andipatin, M. (2020). "What does the university have to do with it?": perceptions of rape culture on campus and the role of university authorities. *South African Journal of Higher Education, 34*(2), 191-209.
- Phipps, A., Ringrose, J., Renold, E., & Jackson, C. (2018). Rape culture, lad culture and everyday sexism: Researching, conceptualizing and politicizing new mediations of gender and sexual violence. *Journal of Gender Studies, 27*(1), 1-8.
- Riwanto, A., Harisudin, M. N., & Firmandiaz, V. (2023). Addressing Campus Sexual Violence: A Collaborative Governance Approach to Legal Policy. *Volksgeist: Jurnal Ilmu Hukum Dan Konstitusi, 225-244*.
- Ross, E., & Rasool, S. (2019). 'You go to campus with fear and come back with fear'. *South African Crime Quarterly, 68*(1), 7-20.
- Rostami, A., Ghazinour, M., Burman, M., & Hansson, J. (2022). Job satisfaction among Swedish police officers: The role of work-related stress, gender-based and sexual harassment. *Frontiers in public health, 10*, 889671.
- South African Polices Services. (2023). Speaking notes for police minister general Bheki Cele (mp) on the occasion of the release of quarter 3 crime statistics in Cape Town on 17 February 2023. Accessed from Services | SAPS (South African Police Service). Retrieved on 27 March 2023.
- Salisu, S. U., Aliyu, B., & Anwar, B. (2021). Establishing Policy and Transparency Unit: A Mechanism for Curbing Sexual Harassment and Corruption in Nigeria Tertiary Institutions.
- Sumi, W. C., Woodbridge, M. W., Wei, X., Thornton, S. P., & Roundfield, K. D. (2021). Measuring the impact of trauma-focused, cognitive behavioural group therapy with middle school students. *School mental health, 13*(4), 680-694.
- Tang, C. S. K., Critelli, J. W., & Porter, J. F. (1995). Sexual aggression and victimization in dating relationships among Chinese college students. *Archives of Sexual Behavior, 24*, 47-53.
- Underwood, J. W. (2019). Impacts of gender-based violence and harassment on graduate student academic functioning.